

QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS ON COLLABORATIVE LAW AFTER THE SPANISH ORGANIC LAW 1/2025, OF 2 JANUARY, ON MEASURES CONCERNING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PUBLIC JUSTICE SERVICE

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What is collaborative law?

Collaborative law is a self-compositional method of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) characterised by its voluntary, confidential, and structured nature, in which the parties to a conflict, assisted by their respective specially trained lawyers and, where appropriate, by neutral expert third parties, work jointly to reach a consensual agreement—whether total or partial—on their disputes, without recourse to the courts. Article 14 of Organic Law 1/2025, of 2 January, on measures concerning the efficiency of the Public Justice Service, establishes it as one of the appropriate means of resolving disputes through non-judicial channels with special regulation¹.

Although collaborative law implies a different conception of legal practice, one that transcends the adversarial model, it is not foreign to the legal profession. The Preamble to Organic Law 1/2025 refers to the Code of Professional Ethics of the Spanish Bar, highlighting the professional conduct of lawyers in the service of concord, along with their obligation to seek an arrangement between the parties. The Preamble also refers to the General Statute of the Spanish Bar, approved by Royal

Article 19 is titled “Collaborative Law Process” and states the following:

1. The parties may avail themselves of a collaborative law process, in which, accompanied and advised each by a practising lawyer duly enrolled in a Bar Association and accredited in collaborative law, and with the participation, where appropriate, of neutral third-party experts in the various matters at issue in the dispute or of communication facilitators, they shall seek a consensual resolution, whether total or partial, of their controversy.
2. The fundamental principles of the collaborative process are: good faith, interest-based negotiation, transparency, confidentiality, teamwork among the parties, their lawyers and any neutral expert third parties who may participate, as well as the lawyers’ waiver of the right to represent their clients before the courts in the event that a total or partial resolution of the controversy is not achieved.
3. Upon conclusion of a collaborative process, the legal professionals who have participated therein shall draft a final record documenting the parties, the participating professionals, the sessions held, the agreements reached, and any matters on which it was not possible to reach an agreement between the parties.

Decree 135/2021 of 2 March, which defines the content of this profession as the activity of advising, counselling, and defending public and private rights and interests, through the application of legal science and technique, in pursuit of two equally weighted objectives: concord, and the effective realisation of fundamental rights and freedoms. In this sense, collaborative law adopts an integrated vision of the needs of persons in conflict.

Where did collaborative law originate?

Collaborative law originated in Minneapolis, Minnesota, United States, in 1990, at the initiative of attorney Stuart Webb, an experienced family law practitioner who became aware that, in many instances, a litigious approach escalates conflict and generates additional problems, to the detriment of the parties, the legal system, society, and the professional themselves. A more efficient resolution of conflict would entail reformulating the role of the legal profession, provided the client wished to address disputes in a more dialogue-oriented manner.

Having become acquainted with Webb's work, Pauline Tesler, an attorney from Marin County (San Francisco), developed this model and introduced the concept of the interdisciplinary team to work with other neutral professionals, always under the lens of a more peaceful and satisfactory resolution of disputes, with the objective of resolving, or attempting to resolve, the underlying problems. In 1999, Tesler contributed to the founding of the International Academy of Collaborative Professionals (IACP).

In the late 1990s, collaborative law spread to Canada, and in the 2000s it reached Europe, with a progressive extension to other continents. Likewise, and without prejudice to non-waivable matters, its expansion is also apparent with respect to the subject matter it addresses, encompassing not only family and succession law, but also neighbourhood, community, business, and corporate disputes, among others.

Is collaborative law regulated in Spain and in other jurisdictions?

Although, at the time of publication of this chapter, no specific national or regional legislation existed, collaborative law is expressly mentioned six times in Organic Law 1/2025.

In certain Autonomous Communities—such as Catalonia, the Basque Country, Madrid, Valencia, and Andalusia—steps have been taken within bar associations and consolidated protocols and training programmes exist, albeit without specific regional normative recognition. Various protocols have nonetheless been signed between bar associations and regional governments to promote its use, which is also provided for in the regulation of free legal assistance. It should be noted, however, that the collaborative process must be flexible and is difficult to regulate in depth or detail.

The United States, the birthplace of collaborative law, presents the most developed—though also the most heterogeneous—normative framework, owing to its federal structure. Texas was the first state to adopt specific collaborative law legislation with the Texas Collaborative Law Act of 2001. In response to the proliferation of disparate state legislation, the National Conference of Commissioners on Uniform State Laws (NCCUSL) developed the Uniform Collaborative Law Act in 2009, subsequently revised and renamed as the Uniform Collaborative Law Rules (UCLR) in 2010. This model uniform law establishes recommended standards for the regulation of collaborative law.

To date, in addition to Texas and without claiming exhaustiveness, the following US states and territories have adopted collaborative law legislation (some based on the UCLA, others with their own legislation): California (2007, Family Code §§ 2013, 2016), North Carolina (2009), Utah (2010), Ohio (2011), Nevada (2011), the District of Columbia (2012), Hawaii (2012), Washington (2012), Minnesota (2013), and Colorado (2013). Other states have adopted partial legislation or incorporated references to collaborative law in their procedural codes.

Although based on common principles, state legislation exhibits variations. For example, some states require specific certified training to practice collaborative law while others rely on professional self-regulation; there are differences in the scope of the confidentiality principle and its exceptions; and divergences exist as to whether requests for precautionary measures terminate or merely suspend the process. Moreover, Texas and several other states have established specialist collaborative law courts. Given this disparate normative development, case law has sought to clarify certain matters—declaring, for example, the clear constitutionality of the clause prohibiting the same collaborative lawyers from intervening in litigation on the same subject matter as the collaborative process, as well as the full validity of the confidentiality principle.

Canada, following its federal structure, has developed regional collaborative law legislation, as well as case law concerning the scope of its principles. Ontario was the first Canadian province to regulate collaborative law through the amended Family Law Act of 2009, which incorporated specific provisions on the matter. British Columbia adopted a Family Law Act in 2012 that includes specific sections on collaborative law, requiring lawyers to inform their clients about alternative dispute resolution methods, including collaborative law, before initiating litigation. Alberta incorporated collaborative law into its Family Law Act of 2003, with mandatory parental education programmes including information on collaborative law and partial public funding for collaborative processes in low-income cases.

Within the common law tradition, mention should also be made of various legislative instruments in territories of Australia, while the United Kingdom presents a model based on professional self-regulation without specific collaborative law legislation, though some statutes do reference it, and with growing professional and judicial recognition.

Most countries of continental Europe lack specific collaborative law legislation, though emerging initiatives exist primarily in Germany, France, the Netherlands, and Belgium.

Recently, Mexico has incorporated “collaborative negotiation” into its positive law through its General Law on Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanisms (Ley General de Mecanismos Alternativos de Solución de Controversias, LGMASC), of 25 January 2024, applicable to any area of law except labour and criminal law. Within Latin America, Argentina’s collaborative law practice also merits particular mention, although no specific legislation exists there.

What would a concrete example of a collaborative law case look like?

The Spanish Ministry of Justice presents on its website the following illustrative example of a collaborative law process, intended merely to convey the wide diversity of possible cases and subject matters:

“Two siblings inherit their parents’ home but disagree over what to do with the property. One wishes to sell it and divide the proceeds, while the other wants to

preserve it as a family legacy. Both decide to use the collaborative law process to resolve their conflict. Each has their own lawyer, and an expert in real estate valuation is also engaged to help them understand the property's actual value. Over the course of several meetings, assisted by the professionals and the process facilitator, the siblings reach an agreement: one will purchase the other's share, and the agreement is formalised in a manner that leaves both parties satisfied without the need to go to court.”

How does collaborative law differ from negotiation between lawyers?

The fundamental distinction lies in the fact that collaborative law constitutes a self-compositional process in which the parties remain the protagonists, while their lawyers and, where appropriate, neutral expert third parties, work together to reach a satisfactory agreement—one that is not conceived as a zero-sum outcome. The Preamble to Organic Law 1/2025 expressly states that, in the face of the exponential increase in litigation, it is appropriate to promote the negotiating role of the legal profession, providing that such activity be duly remunerated—including in cases of court-appointed representation—and introducing a catalogue of assisted negotiation mechanisms, open to any other effective method, that operates as a subsidiary to the direct negotiation activity traditionally practised by lawyers.

Collaborative law is not that traditional negotiating practice, but rather an innovative mode of legal practice. Although both may involve lawyer-assisted negotiation, there are significant structural, procedural, and philosophical differences, as explained below.

The structural difference consists in the existence, within collaborative law, of a clause prohibiting the lawyer who has participated in a collaborative process that did not result in an agreement from subsequently intervening in litigation on the same subject matter. In traditional negotiation between lawyers, no such restriction applies: the lawyer may negotiate and, if no agreement is reached, continue to represent their client in judicial proceedings. The collaborative lawyer assumes a genuine economic risk in the event of process failure (they will lose the client, without prejudice to remuneration for services rendered in the collaborative process), but this aligns their interests with a collaborative resolution that seeks to reconcile the needs and interests of the parties.

At the procedural level, collaborative law requires a formal participation agreement establishing the rules of the process, the principles of good faith, confidentiality, transparency in information exchange, and the commitment not to resort to the courts during the process, among others. Traditional negotiation lacks this structured contractual framework: negotiation discussions tend to be informal or, at best, governed by general procedural norms. Similarly, in the collaborative model the parties commit to the complete and voluntary disclosure of all information relevant to the process, which is not an adversarial evidentiary matter but a proactive form of communication grounded in good faith. Furthermore, the collaborative process is conducted through in-person meetings attended by both parties and their lawyers. This format fosters direct communication, the humanisation of conflict, and mutual understanding. In this sense, within the collaborative process, clients are active protagonists who participate directly in all sessions and decision-making. The lawyer acts as adviser and facilitator, but not as negotiator on the client's behalf. The parties commit to dedicating sustained time and effort to the process, with a structured schedule of meetings.

Collaborative law thus represents a distinct paradigm or philosophy. It explicitly adopts a voluntary, non-adversarial model. The other party is conceived not as an adversary but as a collaborator in the search for a joint solution. The collaborative lawyer seeks to help solve problems and may, to this end, engage professionals from other disciplines (psychologists, therapists, financial specialists, child facilitators, etc.) who assist in managing the emotional and technical dimensions of the conflict. In this sense, collaborative law extends beyond legal knowledge and legal language.

What are the principles of collaborative law?

The fundamental principles of collaborative law cited in Organic Law 1/2025, in addition to voluntariness, are the following six: good faith, interest-based negotiation, transparency, confidentiality, teamwork, and the waiver of legal representation in the same matter. All of these may be explained collectively and in their interrelation as follows.

1. Voluntariness

The collaborative process is strictly voluntary. Both parties must freely choose to participate and may unilaterally withdraw at any time. It cannot be coercively imposed.

2. Commitment Not to Litigate

The parties and their lawyers contractually commit to resolving the conflict without recourse to the courts. If the process fails and litigation is initiated, the collaborative lawyers must withdraw and may not represent their clients in the judicial proceedings. This is the essential distinguishing feature of collaborative law.

3. Transparency

The parties commit to the complete, voluntary, and proactive disclosure of all relevant information. There is no strategic concealment of information. Transparency is a contractual duty, not merely an expectation.

4. Interest-Based Negotiation

The process focuses on identifying and satisfying the underlying interests of both parties, rather than merely defending predetermined positions. Creative solutions are sought that maximise mutual benefit.

5. Good Faith

All parties and participating professionals act in good faith, with honesty, mutual respect, and a genuine commitment to reaching a fair agreement. Bad faith constitutes grounds for terminating the process.

6. Confidentiality

All communications, documents, and negotiations within the collaborative process are confidential and may not be used in subsequent judicial proceedings. This confidentiality safeguards the openness and honesty necessary for the process.

7. Direct Party Participation and a Team Orientation, Potentially Involving Other Professionals

The parties retain control over the process and its outcomes. Solutions emerge from their own will and judgement, not from external impositions. The result must be satisfactory to both parties, not imposed by a third party. The parties participate actively and directly in all meetings and negotiations. They do not delegate entirely to their lawyers. Four-way meetings (both parties and both lawyers present) are the standard modality. Such participation may, where appropriate, take place by remote means (Article 8 of Organic Law 1/2025).

8. Non-Adversarial Approach

The conflict is conceived as a shared problem to be resolved jointly, not as a battle between adversaries. Constructive cooperation is sought, not confrontation. The focus is on building sustainable solutions for the future rather than attributing blame for the past. The future needs of the parties are prioritised and, where relevant, the preservation of their relationships. All interactions among parties and professionals are characterised by mutual respect and recognition of each person's dignity. Offensive or demeaning language is avoided.

9. Dual Legal Representation with a Redefined Role

Each party has their own lawyer who advises and represents them, but the lawyer's role is distinct, entailing a commitment to the collaborative process.

10. Interdisciplinary Approach

The process may incorporate professionals from other disciplines to address the emotional and specific dimensions of the conflict, not merely its strictly legal aspects.

11. Efficiency and Procedural Economy

The process aims to be efficient in terms of time and costs, understood broadly, avoiding unnecessary delays and the expensive procedures of traditional litigation—though without sacrificing the quality of the outcome under pressure for speed.

What third parties may be called upon in a collaborative process and for what purpose?

Without claiming exhaustiveness, the following groups of neutral expert third parties may be distinguished, all of whom are also subject to the principles of the collaborative law process:

1. Psychologists, therapists, social workers, and the like, who assist in recognising and managing emotions, improving communication between the parties, and preparing for meetings.
2. Tax specialists and financial advisers or specialists to provide and explain impartial financial analysis, answer queries, value assets, project future scenarios, and engage in tax planning.
3. Facilitators specialising in working with minors and adolescents who can articulate the needs of children and advise on the impact of decisions.
4. Expert witnesses who can provide technical analyses or resolve queries concerning complex aspects.
5. Mediators or communication facilitators in complex meetings, to manage difficult dynamics, help overcome deadlocks, and so forth.

All such persons share the qualities of neutrality, collaborative commitment, a prohibition on testifying in subsequent court proceedings if the collaborative process fails, confidentiality, and a facilitative function that entails informing rather than imposing decisions. In sum, the aim is to address the legal, emotional, financial, or technical dimensions of the conflict in a comprehensive manner.

Is collaborative law optional?

Yes, the principle of voluntariness is expressly enshrined in the legislation. The choice between collaborative law and traditional negotiation or another avenue—including litigation—must be based on the voluntary agreement of the parties, following the provision of the necessary information and, ideally, a conflict diagnosis that takes into account the relationship between the parties, the complexity of the case, the available resources, and, fundamentally, the genuine willingness of both parties to work collaboratively.

In the second legal ground of the judgment SAP Madrid 564/2021 of 24 May (the sole judicial decision that expressly references collaborative law, beyond general references to Organic Law 1/2025 found in 37 rulings, according to a search of CENDOJ conducted on 12 February 2026), the court states the following clearly:

“the review, where applicable, of maintenance obligations through Collaborative Law will always be optional and will not be mandatory, and the parties may, where appropriate, exercise the actions available to them pursuant to Articles 90 and 91 of the Civil Code, should the conditions provided therein be met.”

We are thus dealing with the principle of party autonomy in dispute resolution. The collaborative process requires the express and concurrent will of both parties to be initiated and maintained.

The initiation of a collaborative law process requires that both parties, together with their lawyers, voluntarily sign the participation agreement. This consent must be informed, meaning the parties must understand:

- The nature of the collaborative process and its characteristics.
- The implications of the clause prohibiting lawyers from acting in subsequent litigation on the same subject matter.
- The commitments to transparency and good faith they undertake.
- The alternatives available (judicial litigation, mediation, arbitration, etc.).
- The potential costs and benefits of this type of process.

If one of the parties does not wish to participate in the collaborative process, it cannot be initiated. Furthermore, the optional character of collaborative law extends throughout the entire process: either party may withdraw unilaterally at any time, without the need to provide justification, thereby terminating the collaborative process.

Accordingly, while the participation agreement creates obligations (of good faith, transparency, confidentiality, etc.), it cannot eliminate the fundamental right of access to justice. The parties commit to attempting a collaborative resolution but retain their constitutional right to resort to the courts if they deem it necessary.

At the same time, in accordance with the applicable codes of professional ethics, the collaborative lawyer must remain alert to any situation where, despite the apparent expression of voluntariness, the collaborative law process cannot function in accordance with its principles and standards—whether because genuine voluntariness is absent, because the level of conflict makes cooperation impossible, or because there are power imbalances that necessitate the protection afforded by the adversarial process.

Is there equal access to collaborative law for all citizens?

Royal Decree 63/2026 of 4 February approved the payment of free legal aid for 2026 and outstanding months of 2025, including legal representation in Appropriate Dispute Resolution Mechanisms (Art. 4.2.4^o), in accordance with Article 11 of Organic Law 1/2025 on the fees of the participating professionals. Along these lines, in 2026 the Ministry of Justice committed to urgently processing the reform of the Free Legal Aid Regulations, updating the remuneration of legal representatives in Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanisms, with an express indication that “this will be compensated at 125% of the amount established for the corresponding procedure, with the aim of incentivising agreements between the parties.” Previously, certain Bar Associations in Spain, with the financial support of regional governments, had already established a list of lawyers available to act, where appropriate on a court-appointed basis, when a beneficiary of free legal aid expressed their wish to use the new dispute resolution methods. In this way, the designation of a professional from the corresponding duty rota (for example, mediation or collaborative law) would be processed. By way of illustration and pending further regulation, concerning the fees payable to the collaborative lawyer—with reference to Annex III of Decree 153/2018 of 30 October on Free Legal Aid—in some Colleges where this rota was provided for, it was indicated that in the event that only a single session was held, €90 would be paid per collaborative professional.

In any event, in various countries with more developed frameworks, some experts consider that the availability of collaborative law primarily benefits parties with sufficient resources to access specialised collaborative lawyers (where they exist) and with the sophistication needed to understand and make the most of the collaborative model. Vulnerable or low-income parties could be excluded due to a lack of real access. For this reason, among other measures, the following would be necessary:

- Developing training programmes and ensuring the availability of collaborative lawyers.
- Establishing free legal aid systems for collaborative law for persons of limited means.
- Raising public awareness of the available options.

Does participation in a collaborative process satisfy the procedural prerequisite for bringing a civil claim?

Yes, pursuant to Articles 5 and 14 of Organic Law 1/2025, which expressly mention collaborative law. This procedural prerequisite applies to claims filed after 3 April 2025, the date of entry into force of Organic Law 1/2025; the date of filing of the claim is the relevant determinative date (see also Articles 264 and 399.3 of the Civil Procedure Act).

With limited exceptions, prior negotiation activity is required as a procedural prerequisite before initiating legal proceedings in all declaratory proceedings under Book II and in the special proceedings under Book IV of Act 1/2000 of 7 January on Civil Procedure.

Is collaborative law always required as a procedural prerequisite for filing a claim?

As noted, prior negotiation activity is required as a procedural prerequisite in all declaratory proceedings under Book II and in the special proceedings under Book IV of Act 1/2000 of 7 January on Civil Procedure, except in proceedings concerning the following matters:

6. Civil judicial protection of fundamental rights.
7. Adoption of measures under Article 158 of the Civil Code.
8. Judicial support measures for persons with disabilities.
9. Filiation, paternity, and maternity.
10. Summary judicial protection of possession or enjoyment of a thing or right from which a party has been dispossessed or whose enjoyment has been disturbed.
11. Applications for summary judicial rulings on the demolition or removal of structures, buildings, trees, columns, or similar objects in a state of disrepair that threaten to cause harm to the claimant.
12. Admission of minors with behavioural problems to specific protection centres, entry into premises for the compulsory enforcement of child protection measures, or the restitution or return of minors in cases of international abduction.
13. Negotiable instrument claims (juicio cambiario).

The procedural prerequisite likewise does not apply to the filing of enforcement claims, applications for precautionary measures prior to filing a claim, applications for preliminary evidentiary proceedings, or the initiation of voluntary jurisdiction proceedings, with the exception of proceedings for judicial intervention in cases of spousal disagreement and in the management of community property, as well as judicial intervention in cases of disagreement in the exercise of parental responsibility. Finally, it is not necessary to avail oneself of an appropriate dispute resolution mechanism prior to submitting an application for a European order for payment pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1896/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 establishing a European order for payment procedure, or for initiating a European small claims procedure pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 861/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 establishing a European small claims procedure.

When is the procedural prerequisite considered satisfied via collaborative law, and how is it evidenced?

In order for the procedural prerequisite to be considered satisfied, there must be an identity between the subject matter of the negotiation and the subject matter of the litigation, even where the claims that might subsequently be brought before the courts on that subject matter could differ. Article 10 of Organic Law 1/2025 establishes that, for the purposes of satisfying the procedural prerequisite, the assisted negotiation activity conducted through collaborative law—or the attempt thereof—must be recorded in documentary form. Proof shall be provided by means of any document signed by both parties recording the identity of the parties and the professionals or experts who have participated in advising them, the date, the subject matter of the dispute, the date or dates of the

meeting or meetings held, and a responsible declaration that both parties have participated in good faith. Failing this, the attempt at negotiation may be evidenced by any document proving that the other party has received the request, invitation, or proposal, on what date, and that they have been able to access its full content. As the Law indicates, the termination of the process without agreement shall be deemed to have occurred, among other alternatives, if thirty calendar days have elapsed from the date of receipt of the initial request by the other party and the first meeting or contact aimed at reaching an agreement has not been held, or if no written response has been received.

Pursuant to Article 10 of Organic Law 1/2025, from May 2025 the Ministry of the Presidency, Justice and Relations with Parliament launched the PIMASC platform, which enables the registration and certification of participation in an alternative dispute resolution process. This platform is accessible to lawyers, legal representatives (procuradores), social graduates, registrars, notaries, economists, and mediators, and will enable the generation of statistical data. The platform issues standardised, validated, and digitally signed documents that may be submitted to the court as evidence of having attempted an out-of-court solution before filing a claim.

Who takes the initiative to engage in a collaborative law process?

Pursuant to Article 5 of Organic Law 1/2025, the initiative to use appropriate dispute resolution mechanisms may come from one of the parties, from both parties by mutual agreement, or from a judicial decision or a referral by the Court Secretary (Letrado/a de la Administración de Justicia) directing the parties to such mechanisms, without prejudice to the fact that collaborative law is fully voluntary for the parties. According to the same article, where all parties propose to use an appropriate dispute resolution mechanism but fail to agree on which to use, the one proposed earliest in time shall be employed.

In many cases, when faced with an emerging conflict, the parties voluntarily choose to attempt the collaborative route as a first option, thereby avoiding the initiation of litigation. This preventive function is one of the fundamental values of the collaborative model. Academic literature demonstrates that the earlier collaborative methods are employed in the conflict cycle, the greater the probability of: preserving the relationship between the parties; reducing economic and emotional costs; reaching more creative and satisfactory solutions; and preventing the escalation of conflict that adversarial litigation produces.

Less frequently, but with growing importance in some jurisdictions, collaborative law may be initiated after a judicial claim has already been filed. In such cases, the parties request the court to stay the proceedings in order to attempt the collaborative process, although—as previously noted—the same lawyers cannot participate. If the collaborative process succeeds, the parties present the agreement reached to the court for judicial approval (where required). If the collaborative process fails, the judicial proceedings resume from the point at which they were stayed, but with the particularity that the collaborative lawyers must withdraw by virtue of the prohibition clause, and are replaced by new legal representatives.

How does collaborative law differ from collaborative practices that may be used in other processes, including adversarial ones?

Collaborative practices, based on negotiation techniques and non-violent communication, among others, may be applied within adversarial proceedings by lawyers trained in collaborative law who, not having acted as collaborative lawyers in the same dispute, may intervene in litigious proceedings where, for example, emotional management and the clarification of interests are required, beyond the deployment of purely legal techniques.

By way of purely illustrative example, the following areas are ones in which collaborative practices are commonly applied: complex commercial negotiations; estate and succession planning; mediation with a collaborative approach; certain administrative sanctioning proceedings that incorporate mechanisms of conformity or conventional termination; collective labour disputes, albeit operating under a specific legal framework (labour legislation, collective bargaining agreements) and with potential intervention by labour authorities.

What matters cannot be dealt with through collaborative law?

Pursuant to Article 4 of Organic Law 1/2025, in the context of family proceedings, conflicts concerning matters that are not at the disposal of the parties under applicable legislation may not be submitted to appropriate dispute resolution mechanisms. However, application is possible in relation to the measures provided for in Articles 102 and 103 of the Civil Code (concerning provisional measures in proceedings for nullity, separation, and divorce), without prejudice to judicial approval of any agreement reached.

Under no circumstances may collaborative law or another dispute resolution mechanism be applied to civil conflicts falling within the competence of the Domestic Violence Sections (Secciones de Violencia sobre la Mujer), nor to disputes concerning matters that are not at the parties' disposal. In particular, the following matters relating to minors are excluded: proceedings opposing administrative decisions of the public body responsible for child protection; recognition of the validity of ecclesiastical rulings; support measures for persons with disabilities; claims of filiation, paternity, and maternity; applications for precautionary measures under Article 158 of the Civil Code; proceedings for the admission of minors with behavioural problems to specific centres; applications for entry into premises for the compulsory enforcement of child protection measures; and measures relating to the restitution or return of minors in cases of international abduction.

Criminal offences, being non-waivable matters, likewise cannot be the subject of a collaborative law process. Furthermore, pursuant to the aforementioned Article 4, any agreement reached through collaborative law must not be contrary to law, good faith, or public policy.

What is the relationship between the collaborative law process and the judicial route?

In addition to potentially serving as a procedural prerequisite prior to filing a claim—as noted above—agreements reached through collaborative law also have legal effect.

Pursuant to Article 13 of Organic Law 1/2025, the agreement reached shall be binding on the parties, who may not bring proceedings with the same subject matter. A challenge to what has been agreed upon may only be brought as an action for nullity on the grounds that invalidate contracts, without prejudice to any opposition that may be raised, where appropriate, in enforcement proceedings.

In any event, collaborative law is a private dispute resolution method with legal recognition, operating in the extrajudicial sphere. Through the participation agreement, the parties create a private framework of assisted negotiation functioning according to collaborative law standards. The parties commit to not initiating judicial proceedings for the duration of the collaborative process, while at all times retaining the power to withdraw from the collaborative process and resort to the courts. In this regard, a request by one party to the other to resolve a matter through collaborative law shall interrupt prescription or suspend the limitation period for actions from the date on which the attempt to communicate the request is recorded (Article 7 of Organic Law 1/2025). Should a specific proposed agreement not receive a response from the counterparty within thirty calendar days of receipt, the limitation period shall restart or resume accordingly. In the event that the initial request for a collaborative law process receives no response, or the process ends without an agreement, the parties must file their claim within one year calculated, respectively, from the date of receipt of the request by the party to whom it was addressed or, as the case may be, from the date of termination of the collaborative law process without agreement.

Upon conclusion of a collaborative process, the legal professionals who have participated shall draft a final record documenting the parties, the participating professionals, the sessions held, the agreements reached, and the matters on which it was not possible to reach an agreement (Article 19.3 of Organic Law 1/2025).

Pursuant to Article 12.3 of Organic Law 1/2025, the agreement may be formalised as follows: the parties may compel one another to elevate the agreement to a notarial deed so that it has the force of an enforceable title. Should the party so requested fail to comply with the request to elevate the agreement to a notarial deed, it may be executed unilaterally by the requesting party, the request being made through the notary authorising the public instrument, who shall record it therein. Where required by law or where the agreement has been reached in a negotiation process to which the parties have been referred by the court in the course of judicial proceedings, the parties may request judicial approval.

In any event, the notary or, as the case may be, the judge, does not assess whether the agreement is the best possible one, but only whether it is legally admissible and adequately protects the interests at stake, particularly if the interests of vulnerable persons may be involved.

Is a collaborative process effective?

In addition to what has been noted above regarding the potential enforceability of agreements reached, as set out in Section IV of the Preamble to Organic Law 1/2025, collaborative law has been internationally validated as a means of facilitating the structured negotiation of parties assisted by their respective lawyers and, where deemed appropriate, by neutral expert third parties who contribute their knowledge of the subject matter or their facilitation of communication. Academic literature on dispute resolution records consistent evidence of greater engagement, higher rates of compliance with agreements, and greater party satisfaction in voluntary processes such as collaborative law. The voluntariness of the parties translates into:

- Greater active engagement in negotiations.
- Higher quality communication.
- More creative solutions better tailored to actual needs.
- A greater probability of voluntary compliance with agreements.

If the process fails, what information must be transmitted to the new lawyers?

Most participation agreements establish that only information falling outside the scope of collaborative confidentiality may be transferred (public documents, objective facts not disclosed during the collaborative process). Negotiating positions, rejected offers, and assessments expressed during collaborative meetings remain confidential and may neither be communicated to the new lawyers nor be used in the litigation.

Do professional associations for collaborative law exist?

The Collaborative Law Association of the Basque Country (Asociación de Derecho Colaborativo de Euskadi, ADCE) was a pioneer in Spain, having been established in 2013. Since then, it has provided numerous training programmes and promoted the development of collaborative law. In June 2014, the Basque Parliament unanimously approved a motion in support of collaborative practice and the private bodies working in collaborative law, which enabled the ADCE to receive a nominated grant from the Basque Government to work on the dissemination and development of collaborative law. Among other bodies in Spain, the Collaborative Practice Section of the Spanish Association of Family Lawyers (Asociación Española de Abogados de Familia, AEAFA) is also noteworthy.

National associations exist in the United States, in the Canadian provinces, in the United Kingdom, Australia, several European countries (Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, and France), Argentina, and Israel, among others.

At the international level, the International Academy of Collaborative Professionals (IACP), founded in 1999, is the principal international organisation promoting professional standards and codes of ethics that serve as a model for national regulations and practices. It also offers international training and certification and organises annual international conferences.

In 2011, the European Association for Collaborative Practice (EACP) was founded, which seeks to promote harmonised legislation within the European Union.

In Latin America, the Latin American Collaborative Law Organisation was created in 2020.

What does it take to become a collaborative lawyer?

By law, one is currently required to be a practising lawyer duly enrolled in a Bar Association and to hold accreditation in collaborative law. Persons trained in collaborative law receive theoretical and practical training in constructive or non-violent communication, emotional management, and interest-based negotiation techniques, exploring the underlying needs of both parties in order to identify shared core values and creative options, with tools for teamwork with other neutral experts.

Becoming a collaborative lawyer implies a profound transformation in one's conception of the profession, the nature of conflict, and the meaning of professional success. It requires a significant investment in training and personal development, but offers the possibility of a more fulfilling professional practice, aligned with constructive values, respect, and the peaceful resolution of problems.

By way of example, the Basque Collaborative Law Association, a pioneer in this field, requires as basic training a syllabus comprising: Harvard Negotiation Basic (NH1); Harvard Negotiation Advanced (NH2); and Collaborative Process (DC), totalling 36 hours. It also offers continuing education through assertive communication and non-violent communication workshops.

May a firm colleague who did not participate in the collaborative process subsequently act as the client’s lawyer in the adversarial proceedings?

The International Academy of Collaborative Professionals (IACP) and the majority of professional collaborative law organisations have adopted a restrictive position: the prohibition extends to the entire firm or legal practice. This restrictive position is grounded in the interpretation of analogous cases or conflicts, as well as in the interpretation of existing legislation and applicable codes of ethics. Furthermore, in practice, even if the same lawyers did not participate directly, there is a risk that confidential information may be shared—formally or informally—within the firm. Likewise, the firm’s financial incentive towards the success of the collaborative process is significantly diluted and may generate mistrust regarding the collaborative commitment.

May a notary conduct collaborative law processes?

The Preamble to Organic Law 1/2025 notes that Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanisms (ADR) enhance the role of the legal professions, with specific reference to the negotiating role of lawyers, but also to the potential role of court representatives (procuradores y procuradoras de los tribunales), mediation professionals, social graduates (graduados/as sociales), notaries, and land and commercial registrars, as well as many other professionals. However, Organic Law 1/2025 refers to the collaborative law process as a practice developed by specialised lawyers, in which the notary may participate as an expert third party where appropriate, or in the elevation of an agreement to a notarial deed.

In the case of other jurisdictions, such as Mexico, some experts consider that recent legislation referring to collaborative law venues would permit lawyers—if duly trained and acting as collaborative lawyers—to operate within notarial offices. In such a context, the notary, while not being a “collaborative lawyer” per se, could advise the lawyers and, if necessary, the “facilitating persons,” to ensure that the agreements they reach satisfy all legal requirements and, where necessary, are elevated to a notarial deed when such form is required for their validity.

What are the phases of a collaborative process?

Collaborative law is governed by a degree of informality and flexibility. In general terms, it may be said to unfold in five structured phases, albeit with flexibility according to the specific needs of each case: initial assessment, formal initiation, information gathering, negotiation, and, where applicable, formalisation of the agreement.

More specifically, reference may be made to the protocol followed by the Bar Association of Bizkaia (Colegio de la Abogacía de Bizkaia), which distinguishes three phases and makes special provision for free legal aid cases.

Phase 1: Pre-Process

14. Information about the collaborative law process and signing of the participation/consent form and data protection documentation.

15. Lawyers making contact with each other and with their clients, and coordinating schedules.

Phase 2: Collaborative Process

2.1 Initiation of the process: Individual meeting between each professional and their client, with the following objectives: building trust and connection through empathetic listening; explaining how the process will unfold, its guiding principles, and the management of documents provided by the parties; identifying the client's emotional state and needs in relation to the collaborative process; detecting positions and "translating" them into interests and needs; detecting blockages and "enemy images" and "translating" them into potential interests and needs that may converge; exploring the best alternative to a negotiated agreement; identifying the most important points to be addressed in the joint meeting; and confirming willingness to participate in the collaborative process and availability of schedule.

2.2 Preparatory team meeting between lawyers, with the objectives of: sharing impressions and relevant matters from each individual meeting; and preparing the joint meeting with lawyers and parties, with specific objectives according to each context and set of needs.

2.3 Four-way joint meeting: Welcome and expressions of gratitude; consideration of how the parties have arrived at this point; what values the parties wish to guide the process; guidelines for dialogue (respecting speaking turns, using first-person language, avoiding accusatory or blaming language, etc.); the Participation Agreement (reading and explaining its content and scope, followed by signature by the interested parties and collaborative professionals); defining the issues to be addressed; facilitating dialogue; noting ideas and proposals on the board; and closing (summary of key points and establishment of next steps, along with a check on how the parties are leaving the meeting). Lawyers shall record the date and duration of the joint session.

2.4 Second (or subsequent) team meeting of collaborative professionals. Joint and team meetings shall alternate with individual meetings as needed. Neutral expert third parties shall be called upon if necessary.

2.5 Final meeting of the parties with the collaborative lawyers: Welcome and expressions of gratitude; reading of the agreement; signing of the final document of total or partial collaborative agreement; and signing of the session register by the parties and lawyers.

Phase 3: Post-Process—Registration and Process Confirmation Documents

16. A brief summary report shall be registered, indicating whether or not an agreement was reached, the number of sessions held, their dates, and the working itinerary followed.

17. Both lawyers shall manage, together with the court representative (procurador/a), the judicial approval of the collaborative agreement or its elevation to a notarial deed. The court representative shall be designated by the College of Court Representatives and shall be linked to the petitioner and their lawyer, but shall act for both lawyers regarding the collaborative process and any needs that may arise in processing and approving the agreement.

18. If the collaborative process concludes without agreement or with partial agreement—and given that both collaborative lawyers will have waived the right to appear in court—a communication shall be sent by email to the Bar Association noting this circumstance, so that it may proceed to arrange the assignment of a duty-rota lawyer for the party benefiting from free legal aid.

What techniques are used in a collaborative law process?

Without claiming exhaustiveness, reference may be made to various techniques encompassing communication, negotiation, emotional management, process structuring, information and transparency, overcoming deadlocks, interdisciplinary teamwork, and closing and sustainability, among others.

Among communication techniques, five may be particularly highlighted: active listening—including body language—reformulation, emotional validation, open-ended questions, and non-violent communication. For example, upon hearing “I want the house,” this may be reformulated as “you need residential stability.” Emotional validation may then be offered: “The text: I understand this is very difficult for you.” Open-ended questions may be used, such as: “What is important to you regarding...?” For preparatory meetings, it is essential to manage expectations, and activities for self-awareness and clarification may also be recommended to the parties.

Among interest-based negotiation techniques are the identification of underlying interests as against apparent positions—repeatedly asking “why” and differentiating needs—generating options without initially evaluating them, considering the best and worst alternatives in the absence of an agreement, assessing existing reality, and attempting to generate mutual gains.

Among emotional management techniques are pauses during periods of high tension—avoiding decision-making at such moments—as well as preparation for difficult conversations with a separation of problems from persons and an understanding of how the problem affects the various parties. Neutral third-party professionals specialising in emotional management and communication may be engaged.

Among process structuring techniques, the emphasis is on clear agendas established in advance, with time allocated to each issue and defined roles, together with an introduction and closing phase to check how the parties are feeling and a final summary of what has been discussed. This approach can prevent backtracking on already agreed points and facilitate the division of complex conflicts into smaller components to be addressed one by one, generating the perception of incremental progress.

Among information and transparency techniques, the use of information disclosure checklists is advisable. Sessions may also be included in which neutral experts explain complex topics and help address any imbalance of knowledge between the parties. Visual aids and infographics may be employed.

Among techniques for resolving impasses or deadlocks, changes of approach and moving on to other points are commonly used, as is seeking a broader or more general perspective, recalling the shared values established at the outset, posing “What if...?” questions, and requesting the assistance of a neutral expert.

With regard to techniques specific to interdisciplinary teams, coordination meetings are required to avoid contradictory or confusing messages, and it may be necessary to assign roles according to knowledge or experience.

Process protection techniques must be made clear from the outset: no interrupting, no threatening, mutual respect; and these must be restated whenever they are not observed. Collaborative lawyers

must remain alert to signs of bad faith and power imbalances that could lead to the termination of the collaborative process.

Among closing and sustainability techniques, scope must be given for imaginative agreement-building—while remaining anchored in reality—and for projecting the agreement into the future. For instance, one may consider how it will function in the medium and long term, and if problems are identified, to include resolution mechanisms in the agreement, as well as clauses for amendment in the event of changing circumstances and mechanisms for resolving future disputes over the interpretation of the agreement. Upon finalising the agreement, there should be a brief celebration and mutual acknowledgement of the collective effort made, fostering a positive orientation towards compliance.

All of the aforementioned techniques are applied in a flexible manner adapted to the specific needs of each case, the personalities of the parties, the complexity of the issues, and the dynamics of the conflict. Collaborative lawyers will know when and how to apply each technique appropriately.

What has been the impact of collaborative law?

Various empirical studies, primarily in the United States and Canada, have documented that collaborative law effectively reduces the caseload of family courts. Some collaborative law associations document their broader social impact.

Furthermore, other studies indicate that collaborative law is contributing to a gradual transformation of legal culture, calling into question the traditional paradigm of the lawyer as an adversarial “fighter” and promoting the model of the lawyer as a “problem-solver” or conflict “peacemaker”. This shift has implications for legal education in law faculties—incorporating skills in collaborative negotiation, constructive communication, and conflict management—as well as for reflection on professional ethics, revaluing the lawyer’s duty to facilitate non-litigious solutions, which could ultimately improve the public perception of the legal profession. This is without prejudice to the fact that there will always be conflicts that the parties do not wish to address, or cannot address, through a collaborative law process.

Case Law

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